

First Record of Wahoo *Acanthocybium solandri* in Turkish Marine Waters

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Abstract

Wahoo *Acanthocybium solandri* in the present study was reported for the first time from Turkish marine waters. *A. solandri* was captured at 40-50 m depth from Üçadalar area in the Antalya Bay on 25 June 2024, and Samandağ coast in 2024 from the İskenderun Bay by Amateur fishermen in the northeastern Mediterranean coast of Türkiye. *A. solandri* is an important recreational fish with high economic value. *A. solandri* was previously reported from two locations in the Mediterranean Sea, and with this report it has reached three in the Mediterranean Sea.

Keywords: *First record, Non-indigenous species, Acanthocybium solandri, Turkish Seas*

Introduction

Wahoo *Acanthocybium solandri* (Cuvier, 1832) is one of the highly mobile and predatory fish species of the oceans in the Scombridae family. Although it has been suggested that this fish is related to billfishes, molecular studies have reported that it is a Scombrid, not an Isthiophorid (Collette et al., 2006). *A. solandri*, which has a slim and aerodynamic body structure, is an important ocean fish for both commercial and recreational fisheries (Oxenford et al., 2003). *A. solandri* is a large epipelagic species distributed in tropical and subtropical temperate waters of the Pacific, Indian and Atlantic oceans (Collette & Nauen 1983). Although their weight is usually between 20-40 kg, the maximum recorded weight is reported to be 96.4 kg. *A. solandri* is preferring sea surface temperatures between

20-30°C, with important habitats including temperature and current gradients, deep ocean ridges, shallow coastal reefs and the proximity of floating debris (Zischke, 2012). Although it is recognized as a highly migratory fish, little is known about the extent of its migration, probably because it moves seasonally.

The first published record of *A. solandri* in the Mediterranean was a single specimen of 144 cm (total length) caught in a tuna trap off Sicily coast of Italy in 1872 in the central Mediterranean (Romeo et al., 2005). According to the same researchers, two more specimens of *A. solandri*, each weighing 15 kg, were caught by harpoon in the Messina strait in 1990. In June 2004, another fish was caught from the same area with a harpoon used in traditional swordfish fishing. In these reports, the specimens caught in the Mediterranean Sea were mainly from Sicily island in Italy.

The second locality record of *A. solandri* outside this region in the Mediterranean was given from the Lebanese coasts in the eastern Mediterranean (Fatfat et al., 2024). Apart from these reports, there is no other record of the presence of *A. solandri* in the Mediterranean.

Hence, we here report the first occurrence of *Acanthocybium solandri* from the Turkish marine waters in northeastern Mediterranean, and third occurrence localities in the Mediterranean.

Material and Methods

Wahoo *Acanthocybium solandri* (Cuvier, 1832) was captured at 40-50 m depth on 25 June 2024 by an amateur fisherman (Figure 1) with in Üçadalar locality of Antalya Bay at the coordinates 36.459928 N, 30.562678 E.

Figure 1. *A. solandri* caught in the Antalya Bay, the northeastern Mediterranean.

Another specimen of *A. solandri* was captured with an underwater rifle rom (Figure2) the coast of Samandağ/Hatay in the İskenderun Bay at the coordinates 36.126556 N, 35.907972 E, the northeastern Mediterranean in 2024.

Figure 2. *A. solandri* spearfished in the coast of Samandağ/Hatay in the İskenderun Bay, the northeastern Mediterranean Sea.

Photographs and videos of both fish captures off the coasts of Antalya and İskenderun Bays were taken and sent to us for species identification. The species identifications of the fish were made from these photographs and videos and other data were obtained by interviewing the fishermen.

Locations where *A. solandri* was caught in the Antalya and İskenderun Bays were given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Map showing the capture sites of *A. solandri* in the Mediterranean Sea. Red circles represent present study records in Turkish marine waters; blue triangles represent previous occurrence records in the Mediterranean. 3.1 and 3.2 represent first and second observations respectively in Turkish marine waters.

Results and Discussion

The species identification of *A. solandri* caught in the Antalya and İskenderun Bays, based on the photographs and videos, revealed that these specimens were wahoo *Acanthocybium solandri*. With this study, *A. solandri* was reported for the first time from the coasts of Türkiye and the number of location records in the Mediterranean reached three.

A. solandri caught at the 40-50 m depth in the Antalya Bay was measured to be 110 cm in total length and 5 kg in weight. This area is a natural reef area that looks like a sunken island in the sea and always has strong currents. The area is within the main currents of the Mediterranean Sea where upwelling occurs due to the collision of the deep currents with the shallowing heel. Morphologically, the fish has a long, fusiform, semi-cylindrical body with dark grey blue vertical bars. The head has a long, pointed conical snout, the mouth has a wide single row of serrated triangular teeth (Figure 4). The fish caught in Samandağ coasts in the Iskenderun Bay were similar in size and weight (Figure 3). On the bases of these two observations, the first occurrence in Turkish marine waters seems to be from the Iskenderun Bay and second occurrence is from Antalya Bay (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Mouth and teeth structure of *A. solandri*.

A. solandri is a fish of tropical and subtropical waters of the oceans. So far, two known locations have been reported for the presence of this fish in the Mediterranean Sea. These locations are the Strait of Messina in Sicily and the Lebanese coast (Romeo et al., 2005; Fatfat et al., 2024). In this study, wahoo were reported for the first time in two different locations from the Turkish Mediterranean coasts, Iskenderun and Antalya Bays. Together with these locations, presence of *A. solandri* from Turkish marine waters at two localities in the Mediterranean Sea were marked (Figure 3). Wahoo is very similar to marrow-barred Spanish mackerel (*S. commerson*). Because of this similarity, some specimens of *A. solandri* caught by fishermen may have been confused with *S. commerson*, which is frequently caught in the eastern Mediterranean Sea.

The Mediterranean Sea is connected to the Red Sea via the Suez Canal and to the Atlantic Ocean via the Strait of Gibraltar by which alien species penetrate to the Mediterranean Sea (Galil, 2008; Turan et al., 2016; Langeneck et al., 2023; Dođdu and Turan, 2024; Uyan et al., 2024). Wahoo *A. solandri* is a fish species naturally living in the Red Sea (Williams et al., 2022). Fatfat et al. (2024) mentioned that Wahoo caught off the coast of Lebanon belong to the Indo-Pacific population and that the passage route of these fish to the Mediterranean may be through the Suez Canal. The same researchers state that the reproduction of wahoo in the Mediterranean, which is an important species in terms of both economic and sport fishing, can make positive contributions. Furthermore, recent genetic studies have reported evidence of differentiation between Indo-Pacific and Atlantic populations of wahoo (Portella et al., 2023). Therefore there might be a genetic bottleneck effect in the populations of *A. solandri* in the Mediterranean Sea. Therefore, further studies are needed on the genetic structure and bioecological status of *A. solandri*.

This is the first report of Wahoo *A. solandri* from the coast of Turkey. With this report, one more species has been added to the alien species Ichthyofauna in Turkish marine waters. *A. solandri* would be an important species in terms of fisheries. On the other hand, there is a lack of data on the ecology, biology, distribution and population status of *A. solandri* in the Mediterranean Sea (Romeo et al., 2005; Fatfat et al., 2024). There is also uncertainty about the ecological impacts of this species on the Mediterranean native species. Therefore, bio-ecological researches are needed on *A. Solandri* in the Mediterranean Sea.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Author Contributions

M.G., C.T., M.S., and A.Y. performed all the experiments and drafted the main manuscript text. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Ethical Approval Statements

Local Ethics Committee Approval was not obtained because experimental animals were not used in this study.

Data Availability Statement

The data used in the present study are available upon request from the corresponding author.

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